

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FORMATION LEADERSHIP QUALITIES OF STUDENTS: WHO CAN HELP?

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ABSTRACT

This article presents materials on leadership qualities of students, their development and maintaining a balanced microclimate in the student environment.

Keywords: leadership qualities of students, tutor.

The modern period of social development in our country opens up wide opportunities for updating the content of education, which makes it possible to form a spiritually rich nation. This determines a new approach to education of student youth. Currently, there is an urgent need for the formation of a creative personality of a future specialist who would be able to solve both daily and large-scale tasks that ensure not just survival, but the progress of the nation. Our current realities require a modern student to have a wide range of opportunities, a developed intellect, the ability for constant self-education and self-improvement, and a focus on creative self-realization. Today, in the context of reforming the education system in Ukraine, the need to develop leadership qualities of students is considered one of the important tasks of higher education.

The problems of developing leadership qualities in students and leadership in general are among the most studied. Among the scientific theories and concepts developed to explain the phenomenon of leadership, one should single out the behavioral theory (R. Blake, S. Jibb, R. Likert, R. Tannenbaum, E. Halpin), attributive theories (D. Joya, H. Sims, F. Fiedler); situational theories (J. Brown, F. Fiedler, E. Wesbur), theory of exchange and transact analysis (J. March, G. Simon, J. Thibault, J. Homans); value models of leadership (K. Hodgkinson, G. Fairholm). The main idea that determines the directions of research in this area is the dilemma: should a leader be born or can one become one? According to researchers who adhere to the first direction, a leader can be formed through the necessary psychological attitudes and exercises. Representatives of another opinion believe that leadership is an innate ability that cannot be learned.

Social psychology interprets the term "leader" as: 1) a member of the group, for whom it recognizes the right to make final decisions; 2) the individual who is endowed with the greatest value potential in the group; 3) an entity that plays a leading role in organizing the group's activities; 4) a person who has a certain influence on individual members of the group and on the group as a whole, regulates relations in it [1, p. 37; 2, p. 54; 5, p. 330]. As in any team, the activity of the leader in the student group is one of the most important factors that determine the styles of joint activity and its result. By virtue of his status, the leader influences the nature of interpersonal relations, which, in turn, determines the state of the psychological climate in the group. The group leader can perform the functions of an initiator

and coordinator of actions, a generator and selector of ideas, a person who guides joint activities and motivates individual members of the group [7, p.233].

In social psychology, a number of classifications of types of leaders have been developed according to several characteristics. According to the nature of the activity, the following are distinguished: 1) a universal leader (one who shows his leadership qualities constantly); 2) situational leader (shows leadership qualities depending on the situation). According to the content of the activity, the following types are distinguished:

I. 1) business leader (one who organizes and manages the activities of the group); 2) a motivational leader (one who directs the group's activities, encourages action); 3) an emotional leader (one who determines the emotional atmosphere in the group) (according to the typology of R. L. Krychevskiy and O. M. Dubovskaia) [3, p. 105];

II. 1) an inspiring leader who determines the activity program; 2) executive leader who organizes the implementation of the already set program; 3) a leader who is both an inspirer and an organizer (according to B. D. Parygin's typology) [6];

III. 1) an intellectual leader who dominates the field of intellectual activity; 2) an emotional and communicative leader who dominates the sphere of leisure; 3) practical leader, the one who leads the implementation of practical activities; 4) universal leader (according to the typology of M. M. Obozov) [4, p. 43].

According to the management style, the following are distinguished: 1) an authoritarian leader (one who has concentrated the leadership on himself, puts himself above the group); 2) democratic (one that shares leadership with other group members, places itself within the group); 3) deviant (one who has distanced himself from the leadership, places himself outside the group). By activity style: leader-creator, leader-fighter, leader-diplomat, leader-advisor, etc.

The leading place of the leader in the system of interpersonal relations within the group necessitates a careful study by the tutor of the students' leadership qualities. It is necessary to periodically determine the degree of coincidence of the awareness of the leadership role with the real influence on decision-making and the contribution to the achievement of the result of joint activities, which is denoted by the concept of "accuracy of the perception of leadership".

It is group tutor who play a leading role in identifying and further developing leadership qualities in students. The role of a tutor, mentor in modern conditions is to help understand and organize, not to impose views, not to replace the student in his activities. For effective work, it is necessary to be able to identify leaders, find them "in the crowd" and provide appropriate work. In order to do this, it is necessary to know the main manifestations of leadership abilities, characteristics of behavior, basic criteria and methods. As with the study of any topic, there are certain problems, so with leadership skills, not everything is so simple.

Student self-government plays a major role in the formation of leadership. It significantly affects the planning of the educational process, the organization of the system of researching the public opinion of students on the most important issues of the life of the educational institution and creates conditions under which the participation of each student in the discussion of problems, acceptance and development of decisions is ensured. The activities of student self-government are directly implemented in the assistance of departments in the organization of Olympiads, publication of faculty newspapers, intellectual, mass cultural and sports events, work of student councils of dormitories. At the same time, students strive not only to realize their artistic talents, but also look for other ways of applying their strength and abilities. This is volunteer work, environmental movement, and political activity. But even here the role of tutors of groups is difficult to overestimate. Their task, like that of the educational institution in general, is to provide its students with the opportunity for self-realization. Involvement in extracurricular activities affects the inner world of a young person, makes it possible to realize such values as responsibility, civic self-awareness, which is necessary for the formation of a person as a leader.

Quite often in an academic group, several students claim leadership status, as a result of which there is a threat of the group splitting into a number of confrontational microgroups. For the tutor of the group, such a situation is quite serious, because it leads to a deteriora-

tion of the moral climate in the team, and the effectiveness of educational interaction decreases. One of the ways out of such crisis situations is to distribute leadership powers and functions, to build a system of situational leadership, to identify and neutralize the influence of authoritarian, destructive and incompetent leaders. With such an approach, it is reasonable to create a package of tasks of an organizational nature for the joint extra-auditory activity of leaders, separate evaluation of the effectiveness of the leader's activity on the part of the teacher, on the part of his team members.

Thus, the tutor must be able to identify leadership abilities in students, develop them and maintain a balanced microclimate in the student environment. But this is only one of his tasks.

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